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PRO-CLIMATE

Proactive community adaptation to climate change
through social transformation and behavioural change

Project Acronym	PRO-CLIMATE
Project Name	Proactive community adaptation to climate change through social transformation and behavioural change
Project Number	101137967
Topic	HORIZON-CL5-2023-D1-01-09 - Behavioural change and governance for systemic transformations towards climate resilience
Type of Action	HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions
Granting Authority	European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA)
Project starting date	1 January 2024
Project end date	31 December 2026
Project duration	36 months

D5.1 Report on the conceptual framework for behavioural change understanding

(Version 1.0)

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D5.1 Report on the conceptual framework for behavioural change understanding

Deliverable Number	D5.1	
Deliverable Name	Report on the conceptual framework for behavioural change understanding	
Work Package No	WP5	
Due Date (month)	M9 (September 2024)	
Submission Date	30 September 2024	
Lead Beneficiary	UiB	
Version	1.0	
Status	First version	
Author name(s)	Ivan Puga-Gonzalez (NORCE) and David Herbert (UiB)	
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Approved by	TERO	
Keywords	Multi agent-based computer model (MACM); computational institutional science (CIS); HUMAT framework; MOA framework; nADICO institutional grammar; Social-Ecological Tipping Point (SETP);	
Type	Report	
Dissemination level	PU – Public	

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Revision history			
Version	Date	Modified by	Comments
0.1	15/08/2024	David Herbert	ToC and first draft
0.2	28/08/2024	David Herbert, Ivan Puga	First circulated draft
0.3	15/08/2024	Catalin Anton, Xu Liu	Feedback to document
0.4	18/08/2024	Iason Tamiakis, Konstantinos Nikolaidis	Review
0.5	21/09/2024	Jacek Baranczuk, Katarzyna Baranczuk	1 st Internal Review
0.6	22/09/2024	Irini Theodorakopoulou, Constantine Iliopoulos	2 nd Internal Review
0.7	27/09/2024	Iason Tamiakis, Ilias Trochidis	Final review and edits
1.0	30/09/2024	Iason Tamiakis	Format and submission

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Abbreviations

CPR	Common Pool Resource
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
HUMAT	Human-Automated (Automated Human) Model
MACM	Multi Agent Computer Model
REA	European Research Executive Agency
SES	Social-Ecological System
SETP	Social-Ecological Tipping Point
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

This paper contains the conceptual basis for a multi-agent computer model designed to assist with the identification of social-ecological tipping points which enable systemic transformations towards climate resilience. After introducing the approach and explaining its advantages and limitations (Section 1), it details how the agents and institutions are conceptualized in the model using a novel combination of established methods in the field, namely the HUMAT and MOA frameworks (Section 2) and the nADICO institutional grammar (Section 3). It explains how these methods can work together to model social processes at inter-personal and inter-institutional levels (Section 4), thus generating the potential for a powerful and realistic simulation of critical processes in making climate change resilient decisions across a range of scenarios and illustrates the approach using examples from the Bergen case study (Section 5).

1 Introduction

1.1 The PRO-CLIMATE Project

The strategic objective of PRO-CLIMATE is to support communities to proactively adapt to climate change through social transformation and behavioural change. To achieve this, PRO-CLIMATE will identify social tipping points and policy actions that enable systemic transformation to be achieved across social systems. PRO-CLIMATE adopts an approach guided by the concept of systems thinking, which views communities as complex systems that are interconnected and influenced by multiple factors, socioeconomic and environmental. By understanding and leveraging their dynamics, it will then develop strategies and interventions that promote social transformation and behavioural change. This will result in a robust framework for designing effective methodologies and tools to foster proactively adaptive behaviours and facilitate transformative changes. A set of diverse (in terms of climate change problems and socio-economic contexts) case studies across Europe will be an instrumental tool for the co-creation, validation, and upscaling of this framework by running living labs and bringing stakeholders together to understand community governance and institutional structures, and to also pilot and validate the project's behaviour change activities.

The outputs of PRO-CLIMATE will include:

- a) the identification of key components of climate adaptation systems, their interactions, systemic interdependencies and trade-offs,
- b) the design, implementation, and evaluation of a living lab framework,
- c) the identification of social tipping points and leverage actions for policy makers,
- d) the development of a multi-agent computer for European socio-ecological systems to allow a realistic analysis of existing and future policy scenarios likely to produce systemic transformations, and
- e) policy recommendations to accelerate systemic change.

1.2 Description of WP5, Benefits and Limitations of the Approach

Description. WP5 of the PRO-CLIMATE project, titled as 'Modelling and stress testing the system', is developing a multi-agent computer model (MACM) of a social-ecological system (SES), using state-of-the-art research together with data and knowledge generated by our six (6) case studies and by other Work Packages (WPs). It is designed to enable the identification of social tipping and leverage points which enable systemic transformations towards climate resilience. From this MACM we will develop a web-based simulation platform to enable policymakers and other stakeholders to make realistic prospective analyses of existing and future policy impacts tailored to their own contexts.

The **benefits** of the approach used are highlighted by a recent review of the *Computational Institutional Science Agent Based Modelling* (CIS-ABM) state-of-the-art:

CIS-ABM applications can help researchers move beyond traditional barriers in social science inquiry (e.g., one-time, self-reported data [like surveys] providing only a snapshot of social phenomena) and towards investigations of institutional phenomena with more depth, length, and breadth. ... as scholars have further developed its capacity, ABM has become increasingly viable for: (1) exploring the emergent social patterns and equilibria of endogenous institutions and (2) building and evaluating theories through the simulation and replication of various dimensions of exogenous institutions. ... ABM can control for confounding factors surrounding decision-making within institutionalized settings and establish causality between changes in agents, interactions, environments, and emergent outcomes through computer simulation experiments. (Oesterling et al. 2024: 427)

Thus, CIS-ABMs facilitate the investigation of the dynamics of SESs, identifying causal links and enabling researchers to see how the interaction between agents and institutions is likely to play out over time under different conditions. The approach has been used to model the impacts of land-use management on ecosystem services and biodiversity (Habib et al., 2016), flood protection

investment as a coupled human-natural system (O’Connell and O’Donnell 2013), and the interaction of endogenous and exogenous institutions in managing forests (Vallino 2014). We will build on and contribute to this body of work, particularly that which has been developed around the management of common pool resources (CPRs), building on Elinor Ostrom’s work in conceptualising co-operative and sustainable management of these, combining Ostrom’s (1990, 2005) analysis of institutions with approaches from social marketing and behavioural change research (Rothschild 1999; Andreason 2002).

Limitations. CIS-ABMs are not predictive models, but they enable researchers to:

... explore futures in which there is deep uncertainty. Under such situations accurate predictions are not possible (Lempert, 2002; Bankes, 2002). However, given that ABMs correspond quite closely to the ways that individual stakeholders generally think about actions and interactions, there is the potential for model appraisal, and for actors/stakeholders to gain insight into the decision-making process that they seek to influence. A model can be deemed useful if stakeholders view it as plausible and it enables them to explore the consequences of actions that they may wish to undertake (Moss et al., 2001). Such participatory agent-based simulation has proved useful in exploring the achievement of policy objectives with stakeholders. (O’Connell & O’Donnell 2013: 165)

A more specific limitation is that we have developed the initial conceptualisation in reference to the Bergen case, one of six case studies on PRO-CLIMATE. This is partly because of limited data on other cases at the time of writing, as system analysis on the project is distributed across multiple work packages, conducted on different timescales and is at an early stage. But this is not an unusual procedure - model conceptualisation needs to begin somewhere, and often proceeds from a particular case, then builds towards greater generality (Layder 1998). While this shapes design decisions, modifications can be made as further information (from other cases and literature) becomes available; the steps of model development are connected by multiple iterative loops, especially between steps 1 and 3 (see 1.3 below). In developing the model, we have chosen to focus on social and political processes which produce land use decisions relevant to building climate change resilience in SESs, and which involve the management of a common pool resource/threat (e.g. land, water, air, carbon sink). Such decisions are critical to building climate change resilience in many SESs, and occur across a wide range of contexts, giving the model wide potential relevance.

1.3 The Process of Developing a MACM

The development of an MACM of a social-ecological system may be broken down into five (5) steps (Ghorbani 2022: 3):

1. System analysis
- 2. Model conceptualization** (the focus of the current deliverable)
3. Detailed design
4. Implementation
5. Evaluation (in this case, the development of a web-based platform customised from the MACM)

In the system analysis step, information is gathered about stakeholders, the decision-making process, the social context and institutions, stakeholder interactions and the ecological context and challenges (ibid.). Using this information, previous modelling experience, and literature review, the conceptual model is developed, which is the purpose of the current document. We have chosen to model the production of social tipping points at two levels of social interaction – (i) individuals or organizations mobilizing in response to a particular threat, challenge or opportunity, and (ii) organizations/institutions interacting to decide about the management of a common pool resource/threat. This two-step process is common in many scenarios, and, while it is complex to model, it offers the prospect of more realistic modelling.

1.4 Research Questions and Social-Ecological Tipping Points

We have identified two research questions which correspond to the two social-ecological tipping points that we are attempting to model. These are:

- (a) *Under what conditions – and by what mechanisms - do individuals form groups (e.g. environmental NGOs, ENGOs) which mobilize in favour of climate change resilient land use decisions?*
- (b) *Under what conditions – and by what mechanisms - do local governments make climate change resilient land use decisions?*

PRO-CLIMATE aims to identify social tipping points which may be leveraged to scale up climate change resilient actions and measures. A tipping point is a threshold in a system, where a small change in conditions or an action can produce rapid changes in the system’s operation, usually through one or more self-reinforcing feedback mechanisms. **A social-ecological tipping point (SETP) occurs when a small change in social action results in a large change in environmental consequences.** For example, policy, legal or administrative decisions may set precedents which have a multiplier effect through a social-ecological system, or thresholds in infrastructure provision or pricing, which make renewable energy solutions more attractive (Sharpe and Lenton 2020). Within PRO-CLIMATE, we are interested in identifying conditions in the SESs that we model, which produce positive social-ecological tipping points or SETPs.

The two SETPs we have identified to model are (a) the point at which concerns about the environmental consequences of land development proposals shared in a social network produce activist group formation and (b) the point at which competing pressures at institutional level - including from activist groups of type (a) - produce pro-climate change resilient land use decisions. The two levels of social processes and SETPs we are modelling are depicted in Figure 1:

Figure 1: Two levels of social processes and SETPs

The examples in the figure refer to the Bergen case as the pilot case, but we intend that these levels of social processes will also be identifiable in the other cases and adapted accordingly, enabling their use to refine the model and produce a simulation platform of wider applicability.

2 Model Conceptualization

The remainder of this document outlines a tentative conceptualization for an agent-based model to be developed as part of WP5 of the PRO-CLIMATE project. The main goal of this model will initially be to simulate the dynamics related to the formation of activist groups of citizens concerned about climate change relevant to land use, and the influence of those groups once formed and mobilised on the wider negotiation processes that inform policies and decisions around those issues. In other words, the model is designed to capture the micro-level behaviours and interactions among simulated agents (including institutions) that can lead to tipping points at two levels which impact the macro-level of the socio-ecological system. The first level is the process through which the attitudes and behaviours of citizen agents develop individually and collectively in response to new information and events, leading to the formation of an activist group which engages with policy makers and institutions to attempt to influence decisions about land use. The second level is the dynamic between activist groups with other actors and institutions which tips the system in a way that produces a decision that will help build climate change resilience across the SES.

One way to combine the two research questions stated at 1.4 is as follows:

Under what conditions - and by what mechanisms - do climate adaptation-oriented citizen groups form and subsequently influence negotiation processes related to land use?

However, note that this formulation, while useful in linking the two levels of social action, directs inquiry towards activist groups' influence on decision-making processes at institutional level, which may not be the most important factor in relations at this level.

In each of the sections below, we explain why we designed each aspect of the model in the way we did. We articulate our initial assumptions about the agents and interaction rules and clarify how these design decisions are related to the wider goals of WP5 and the other relevant work packages in the PRO-CLIMATE project.

2.1 The Human-Automated (HUMAT) model

The human-automated (HUMAT) model integrates theoretical concepts related to human motives, cognitive dissonance, and individual and social decision-making strategies within social contexts such as networked communities. This model facilitates the simulation of decision-making scenarios where individuals must choose between two or more options, such as deciding whether to adopt a new technology or support a cause. By simulating these scenarios, we can better understand how factors such as individuals' motives, opportunities, and abilities, as well as social environments and interactions, influence both individual behaviours and collective outcomes within complex socio-economic systems.

2.1.1 Motives in HUMAT

In the HUMAT model each agent represents a human person that is influenced by three types of motives:

1. **Experiential Motives:** factors like safety, convenience, pleasure/emotion, and familiarity.
2. **Social Motives:** the desire for social approval from others.
3. **Value Motives:** principles/attitudes such as justice, freedom, equality, and transparency.

Each motive has a certain importance, which indicates how relevant it is to the agent. Motives guide the decision-making process. When facing a decision among different choices, agents evaluate how each choice satisfies each of its motives. Satisfactions range from negative to positive, where negative values are dissatisfying, and positive values are satisfying. Choices may satisfy motives differently. For instance, choosing a vegetarian food may be dissatisfying for a person used to eating meat (an experiential motive), but satisfying if this person is concerned about animal welfare (a value motive).

2.1.2 Social Networks in HUMAT

HUMAT agents are embedded within social networks, where each agent's social connections are termed their ego network. Within this network, the ego refers to the focal agent, while alters denote the agents connected to ego. For each alter, ego holds a mental representation of their preferred choice, persuasions, and satisfactions. Whenever the ego and an alter interact this information is updated. Thus, during the simulation, alters may change their choices and related values without ego being immediately aware of it. Information is only updated upon interaction, which means that if no interaction occurs, HUMAT agents may hold false beliefs about alters' preferred choices and satisfactions.

2.1.3 How Agents Make Decisions

When an agent faces a decision, it evaluates how each choice satisfies its motives. For example, imagine a person deciding whether to switch to a vegetarian diet. Experiential motives might include pleasure from eating meat (negative satisfaction) and health benefits from vegetables (positive satisfaction). Social motives might involve wanting to fit in with friends who are vegetarians (positive satisfaction) or worrying about being teased by meat-eating friends (negative satisfaction). Value motives could include caring for animal welfare (positive satisfaction) and personal freedom to choose any diet (negative satisfaction).

To make a decision, agents calculate a total satisfaction score for each choice. This is done by considering how well the choice meets the satisfaction levels of all motives and combining these with the importance of each motive. The choice with the highest total satisfaction score is initially selected by the agent (eq. 1).

$$TS_c = \frac{\sum_{m=1}^N S_{c,m} * I_m}{N} \quad \text{eq. 1}$$

Where:

- TS_c is the total satisfaction of choice c
- $S_{c,m}$ is the satisfaction of choice c for motive m (for $m = 1, 2, \dots, N$)
- I_m is the importance of motive m
- N is the total number of motives

At the start of the simulation, agents make choices based solely on their experiential and value motives. After making this initial choice, agents observe what choices others in their social network (ego network) make. They then reevaluate their choice, considering all motives, including social motives. The satisfaction derived from social motives depends on the proportion of agents in the ego network preferring a given choice (eq. 2). This means that if many people in the ego network make a particular choice, the social motive satisfaction will be higher when the agent selects that particular choice. Following the previous example, an agent that initially decides to go vegetarian for health (experiential) and animal welfare (value) motives, might then notice that many friends are still eating meat (social motive), leading it to reassess its decision based on this new social information.

$$S_{c,m} = PA_c * 2 - 1 \quad \text{eq. 2}$$

Where:

- $S_{c,m}$ is the satisfaction of choice c for social motive m
- PA_c is the proportion of alters selecting choice c

2.1.3.1 Dealing with Tie Choices

If the total satisfaction score of the top two choices is very close (within 10%), the agent further analyzes its decision based on dissonance status. Dissonance status measures how conflicted an agent feels about a choice. It's calculated by looking at how the choice satisfies or dissatisfies the agent's various motives. For each choice, positive (satisfying) and negative (dissatisfying) motive

scores are summed up separately. The smaller of these two sums is denoted the *dissonant* value, and the larger sum the *consonant* value. Dissonance status is then calculated (eq. 3). This value helps determine if an agent is comfortable with its choice. A higher value means more conflict and discomfort, while a lower value means less conflict. Going back to our example, if the person feels strong positive satisfaction from health and animal welfare (value) but strong negative satisfaction from social disapproval, it has a high dissonance status and might feel conflicted about its decision.

$$Dissonance\ Status_c = \frac{2 * Dissonant_c}{Consonant_c + Dissonant_c} \quad eq. 3$$

Once dissonance statuses are calculated for each choice, agents select the choice with the lowest dissonance status, as long as the difference between the lowest and the second lowest is less than 10%. If not, they reconsider their decision-making process. If reconsideration is needed, agents reassess their total satisfactions based solely on their experiential and value motives (eq. 1) and select the choice with the highest satisfaction. If the total satisfactions scores are still too close, they choose randomly between the top choices.

2.1.3.2 Agent's Happiness with Their Choice

After making a choice, agents check their happiness by measuring *dissonance strength*, which measures how much psychological conflict or discomfort they feel about their choice. *Dissonance strength* is calculated based on how the dissonance status compares to the agent's tolerance for dissonance, i.e., its ability to handle conflict (eq. 4). If *dissonance strength* is high, the agent feels uncomfortable and may seek to alleviate this discomfort.

$$dissonance\ strength_{sc} = \frac{dissonance\ status_{sc} - dissonance\ tolerance}{1 - dissonance\ tolerance} \quad eq. 4$$

2.1.3.3 Agents' Dilemmas

When agents experience high dissonance strength (conflict or discomfort) after making a choice, they first determine the type of dilemma they are facing: social or non-social.

- Social dilemmas occur when the choice has at least one negative (dissatisfying) social motive score and at least one positive (satisfying) non-social motive score.
- Non-social dilemmas occur when the choice has at least one negative (dissatisfying) non-social motive score and at least one positive (satisfying) social motive score. If all motive scores for a choice are either positive or negative, the agent faces no dilemma.

In our previous example, an agent going vegetarian feels social disapproval (negative social motive) because most alters are meat-eaters, but it values animal welfare (positive non-social motive), thus creating a social dilemma. Conversely, if it feels social approval (positive social motive) but dislikes the taste of vegetables (negative non-social motive), it's a non-social dilemma.

2.1.3.3.1 Addressing Social Dilemmas

When facing a social dilemma, the agent will signal to others in their social network. The agent identifies an individual (alter) in its network who:

1. has chosen differently
2. has not been signalled before
3. has the highest *signal persuasion*.

Signal persuasion is a measure of how much influence the agent (ego) has over the selected individual (alter). This influence depends on ego's passion or determination to make its opinion compelling (*aspiration* level) and the extent to which they share common ground in terms of their motives' satisfactions and importances (Box 1).

Box 1.

Signal Persuasion is calculated according to equation 5:

Where:

- 6) *Alter's aspiration signal* is a value representing the degree of persuasion of ego over the alter (eq. 6)
- $S_{l,c,m}$ denotes the degree of similarity between ego's and alter's satisfactions and importances for each choice c and motive m (eq. 7)

where AL denotes *aspiration* level, a variable representing how much influence has one agent over the other and varying in the continuum $[0,1]$. Thus, if ego's AL is larger than the alter's AL , ego's has a medium/large degree of persuasion over the alter. On the other hand, if the alter's AL is larger or much larger than ego's AL , ego's has low or null persuasion over the alter.

The similarity index, $S_{l,c,m}$, is calculated according to eq. 7

Where:

- $I_{m,a}$ is the importance of motive m for the alter
- $I_{m,e}$ is the importance of motive m for ego
- abs is the absolute difference
- $MIS_{c,m,a}$ is the motive impact score of choice c and motive m for the alter (eq. 3)
- $MIS_{c,m,e}$ is the motive impact score of choice c and motive m for ego (eq. 3)

Condition one in equation 7 is met only when the MIS values for the alter and ego are aligned, i.e., both are either positive or negative. Hence, the similarity index depends on whether the MIS are aligned and on the difference in importance that ego and alter give to motive m . The SI index has a maximum value of 0.4, when MIS are aligned and motives' importances are the same; and a minimum of 0, when MIS are misaligned. S 's are then weighted by the alter's aspiration signal (eq. 5).

During signalling, the selected alter then updates its mental representation of the ego's choice, persuasiveness and satisfactions; while ego (i.e. the focal agent, embedded in a social network) updates its mental representation of the alter's preferred choice. For instance, ego might tell a meat-eating friend about the health benefits and animal welfare reasons for going vegetarian, hoping to influence the friend's choice and reduce their own social discomfort.

2.1.3.3.2 Addressing Non-Social Dilemmas

When facing a non-social dilemma, the agent will inquire others in their social network. The agent selects an alter who:

1. has chosen differently
2. has not been inquired before
3. has the highest *inquire persuasion* value

Inquire persuasion is a measure of how much influence the alter has over ego. This influence depends on the alter's determination to make its opinion compelling (its *aspiration* level) and the

extent to which they share common ground in terms of their motives' satisfactions and importances (Box 2).

Box 2.

During inquiring, ego updates its mental representation of the alter's choice, persuasiveness, and

Inquire persuasion is calculated according to equation 8:

Where:

Alter's aspiration inquire is a value representing the degree of persuasion of the alter over ego (eq. 8)

$SI_{c,m}$ denotes the degree of similarity between ego's and alter's satisfactions and importances for each choice c and motive m (eq. 7)

The *alter's aspiration inquire* is calculated according to equation 9:

Hence, if alter's AL is larger than ego's AL , the alter has a medium/large degree of persuasion over ego. On the other hand, if ego's AL is larger or much larger than alter's AL , the alter has low or null persuasion over the ego.

satisfactions. The alter updates its mental representation of ego's preferred choice. So, for instance, ego might ask a vegetarian friend about tasty vegetarian recipes to see if this reduces their dissatisfaction with the diet's taste.

2.1.3.3.3 Mixed Dilemmas

If the agent faces both social and non-social dilemmas, it decides at random whether to signal or inquire.

2.1.4 Model's loop and end

After signalling or inquiring, agents update their social motive satisfactions according to the new proportions of choices in their network. They then reevaluate their happiness with their choice. If they remain unhappy, they identify the type of dilemma and take action again. The process continues until no more changes in preferred choices are observed at the population level or the changes become stable.

2.2 The MOA Framework and behaviour change

2.2.1 The MOA Framework

The motivation, opportunity and abilities (MOA) framework was originally developed by MacInnis et al. (1991) as individuals' drivers influencing the communication effectiveness of brand information from an ad. Rothschild (1999) further developed the framework and applied it to social marketing and behavioural change. Where social marketing is an approach aiming at maintaining/changing people's behaviours for their own benefit and that of the society, particularly health related behaviours (Rothschild 1999; Andreasen 2002). This framework has now found its way into several studies related to behaviour change, going from behaviours related to food loss and waste (Vittuari et al. 2023) to energy-saving ones (Li et al. 2019). In all these cases, they identified motivations, opportunities and abilities as the main factors affecting behavioural change. Similarly, Michie and colleagues (2011) have also developed a framework for behaviour change called COM-B (capability, opportunity, motivation, behaviour). The COM-B and MOA framework share the same drivers for behaviour change except that in the COM-B framework, ability is referred to as capability. Nevertheless, the definition of each element in both frameworks is the same, and hereafter we will refer to the behaviour change framework as MOA.

Besides MOA and COM-B, there exist many other frameworks that classify behavioural change, but they have been criticised for lacking comprehensiveness and coherence (Michie, van Stralen, and West 2011). The MOA framework, however, captures both internal mechanisms (psychological and physical) and external environmental factors that ultimately affect the individual (Michie, van Stralen, and West 2011). This makes the MOA framework particularly suitable for our model, which features individual processes and their interactions with the environment.

The MOA framework posits three main drivers for behaviour change (Michie, van Stralen, and West 2011; Rothschild 1999; Andreasen 2002; Maclnnis, Moorman, and Jaworski 1991).

1. **Motivation:** defined as goal-directed arousal, it involves brain processes that energize and direct behaviour, such as habitual processes, emotional responses, and analytical decision-making.
2. **Opportunity:** Refers to environmental factors that enable or disable the possibility of enacting a given behaviour.
3. **Abilities:** Relates to the individual’s psychological and physical capacity to engage in the behaviour, including the necessary knowledge and skills.

These three elements play a crucial role influencing the behaviour itself (Figure 1). However, whereas all authors agree that opportunity and ability can influence the individual’s motivations and that motivation enables the behaviour (Michie, van Stralen, and West 2011; Rothschild 1999; Andreasen 2002; Maclnnis, Moorman, and Jaworski 1991); Michie and colleagues (2011) also suggest that abilities and opportunities directly enable the behaviour and that the behaviour in turn can also influence these three elements (double headed arrows in Figure 2).

Figure 2: The MOA Framework

2.2.2 Drivers of Behavior Change in the MOA System

How and why do behaviours change In the MOA system? When no internal (individual) or external (environmental) forces act on any of its components (Figure 2), the system will remain stable, meaning the behaviour enacted by an individual will always be the same. An intervention, however, may change one or more of the components of the system potentially leading to a change in behaviour. Thus, the MOA framework provides a basis for intervention design, allowing us to hypothesise which component(s) of the behavioural system needs to be targeted to achieve behavioural change. In other words, the appropriateness of an intervention depends on the presence (or absence) and degree of motivation, opportunity and ability of the target audience, which, in turn, determine how likely a person is to perform, resist or be unable to perform a given behaviour (Rothschild 1999). Rothschild (1999) categorises interventions in three types: education, marketing and law.

Rothschild (1999) refers to *education as a communication tool that attempts to inform/persuade the receiver to voluntarily abstain, stop, or adopt a particular behaviour without providing any kind of reward or punishment.* Education, thus, creates awareness about the existing benefits of behaving

in a particular manner and may influence the behaviour via individuals' motivation and/or abilities. Note that Michie et al. (2011) also suggest persuasion, training (imparting skills), and modelling (providing examples) as interventions distinct from education. However, here we consider all these as falling within the education category because they all aim to influence behaviour through the acquisition of knowledge, skills, and attitudes.

Marketing refers to the management of behaviour via the offer of incentives that can be accepted or rejected within a given environment (1999). Thus, by creating alternative choices in the environment, marketers attempt to manage behaviour via a voluntary self-interested exchange. A key difference with education is that, whereas education creates awareness of the benefits of a behaviour, it leaves up to the individual to figure out how to make the behaviour change; marketing, on the other hand, provides a timely and explicit payback. Marketing, thus, may promote behavioural change by the creation of new alternatives or opportunities in the environment and, thus, affect the opportunity element of the behavioural system. Similar to education, Michie et al. (2011) breaks down marketing into several other categories: incentivisation, environmental restructuring, and enablement.

Law involves the use of coercion to achieve behaviour change via punishment for noncompliance. Law demands non-voluntary behaviour in exchange for lack of punishment, whereas in education and marketing behavioural change is voluntary. Nevertheless, law may offer opportunities, when desirable behaviour may be hindered via social norms (i.e., pressure to conform). Hence, even though the law may, in certain cases, provide opportunities, in most cases, such an intervention is contemplated, when attempts to increase motivation and opportunities fail. Michie et al. (2011) breaks down law into coercion and restriction.

From the three MOA elements, motivation appears to be the most important one because, even if the environment provides incentives and alternatives, if there is no motivation there will not be behavioural change. Motivation, thus, persuades the individual to execute a behaviour and marketing facilitates its enacting. Further, when both abilities and opportunities are present, motivation most likely follows. Rothschild (1999) provides a map for the type of interventions needed depending on the combination of presence/absence of the MOA elements.

Applications of Education, Marketing, and Law

MOTIVATION		yes		no	
		yes	no	yes	no
OPPORTUNITY		yes	no	yes	no
ABILITY	yes	<p>①</p> <p>prone to behave</p> <p><i>education</i></p>	<p>②</p> <p>unable to behave</p> <p><i>marketing</i></p>	<p>③</p> <p>resistant to behave</p> <p><i>law</i></p>	<p>④</p> <p>resistant to behave</p> <p><i>marketing, law</i></p>
	no	<p>⑤</p> <p>unable to behave</p> <p><i>education, marketing</i></p>	<p>⑥</p> <p>unable to behave</p> <p><i>education, marketing</i></p>	<p>⑦</p> <p>resistant to behave</p> <p><i>education, marketing, law</i></p>	<p>⑧</p> <p>resistant to behave</p> <p><i>education, marketing, law</i></p>

Michie et al. also (2011) present a diagram, the behavioural change wheel (BCW), with a more nuanced categorization of the type of possible interventions, also linking them to the MOA element they may affect. Yet, they do not make recommendations as to what types of interventions could be used based on the presence/absence of the MOA elements.

Table 2 Links between the components of the 'COM-B' model of behaviour and the intervention functions

Model of behaviour: sources	Education	Persuasion	Incentivisation	Coercion	Training	Restriction	Environmental restructuring	Modelling	Enablement
C-Ph					√				√
C-Ps	√				√				√
M-Re	√	√	√	√					
M-Au		√	√	√			√	√	√
O-Ph						√	√		√
O-So						√	√		√

1. Physical capability can be achieved through physical skill development which is the focus of training or potentially through enabling interventions such as medication, surgery or prostheses.
2. Psychological capability can be achieved through imparting knowledge or understanding, training emotional, cognitive and/or behavioural skills or through enabling interventions such as medication.
3. Reflective motivation can be achieved through increasing knowledge and understanding, eliciting positive (or negative) feelings about behavioural target.
4. Automatic motivation can be achieved through associative learning that elicit positive (or negative) feelings and impulses and counter-impulses relating to the behavioural target, imitative learning, habit formation or direct influences on automatic motivational processes (e.g. via medication).
5. Physical and social opportunity can be achieved through environmental change.

Further, they go beyond interventions since they also make a typology of potential policies and they link the policy to the intervention type.

Table 3 Links between policy categories and intervention functions

	Education	Persuasion	Incentivisation	Coercion	Training	Restriction	Environmental restructuring	Modelling	Enablement
Communication/Marketing	√	√	√	√				√	
Guidelines	√	√	√	√	√	√	√		√
Fiscal			√	√	√		√		√
Regulation	√	√	√	√	√	√	√		√
Legislation	√	√	√	√	√	√	√		√
Environmental/social planning							√		√
Service Provision	√	√	√	√	√			√	√

Finally, Andreasen (2002) suggests that there are three societal levels at which interventions can be directed and have an impact: the individual, community and structural level. The individual refers to the person, who ultimately must change its behaviour. The community level refers to the dynamics of social norms, interpersonal influence, diffusion processes and local leadership as important factors also determining individuals' behaviours. The structural level refers to social structures, such as laws, institutions, available technologies, public policies constraining and enabling behaviour change. On the basis of these three levels, they further expand the typology of interventions, according to each MOA element.

Figure 1. Possible Collaboration of Approaches Given the Source of Barriers to Action

Problem	Barrier	Role for Social Marketing	Role for Community Mobilization	Role for Structural Change Approaches
Motivation	Individual	Creating awareness; promoting high benefits, low costs	Urging media cooperation	Building Web links to hard-to-reach people
	Community	Urging opinion leaders to motivate others	Creating awareness; raising public concern	Creating incentives for group organization
	Structural	Urging change in structural rewards/penalties (e.g., taxes)	Holding briefings	Changing structural rewards/penalties (e.g., taxes)
Opportunity	Individual	Creating awareness of behavioral opportunities	Urging business, political cooperation	Changing economic barriers to individual action
	Community	Urging businesses to provide access to change agents	Changing repressive social norms	Eliminating antitrust restriction on business cooperation
	Structural	Urging use of government facilities for programs	Bringing pressure to bear on legislators	Providing government subsidies; changing physical environments
Ability	Individual	Providing modeling of ideal behavior	Pointing group members to individualized change tools	Allowing government agencies to provide training
	Community	Providing communications tools for outreach	Conducting group training	Allowing government premises (e.g., schools) for group training
	Structural	Urging removal of public disincentives	Changing community structures voluntarily	Removing public disincentives

An overlooked aspect of the MOA framework is its failure to account for individual social interactions and the heterogeneity of people. The HUMAT model addresses these limitations by recognizing that individuals are embedded within social networks, where interactions can significantly influence their decisions and behaviours. Additionally, HUMAT allows for individual heterogeneity, such as variations in socio-demographic factors, which can affect the importance assigned to motives and the satisfaction derived from them.

3 Institutions

3.1 Definitions: Institutions and institution types

In the ABM and economics literatures, institutions tend to be defined as patterns or regularities in human behaviour, e.g. “enduring regularities of human action in situations structured by rules, norms, and shared strategies, as well as by the physical world” (Crawford and Ostrom 1995). This perhaps differs from vernacular (and some sociological) conceptions of institutions as concrete organizations such as schools, hospitals, charities, the police, media, government etc. However, there is a clear connection between these different concepts, because it is largely through these concrete organizations (alongside more informal social processes) that the regularities of action highlighted by ABM modelers and economists are produced. Social institutions structure human action through diverse social and communication processes, including education (schools), monitoring and sanctions (the police), encouragement and organization (charities), exposure to information and framing (media) and so on. And it is the regularizing impact of such processes on human action that we will seek to capture by modelling institutions in the PRO-CLIMATE ABM.

Furthermore, we seek to capture two kinds of institutional processes highlighted by our integrated research question:

Under what conditions - and by what mechanisms - do (a) climate adaptation-oriented citizen groups form and (b) subsequently influence negotiation processes related to land use?

Thus, (a) refers particularly to the formation and impact of *endogenous* institutions – ‘those that emerge from a bottom-up perspective as a group of individuals engages in collective, grassroots processes of institutional development and implementation’ (Oesterling et al. 2024: 417), while to address (b) we also need to consider *exogenous* institutions: ‘those that are designed and enforced by some hierarchical authority [e.g. government, law, police] from a top-down perspective’ (ibid.) - although we suggest that such institutions may have coalesced over time from informal processes (i.e. accrued from tradition and become embedded in culture) rather than having been ‘designed’.

3.2 Modelling Institutions

Our conceptualisation of institutions is influenced by Common Pool Resource theory (CPR) developed by Elinor Ostrom (1990, 2005) to understand the sustainable management of finite common resources (including natural resources like land, water and air), and to ‘get away from [neoclassical economics] under-socialised view of humans and ... to explain why, in so many cases, communities overcome problems that neoclassical economics says should cripple them’ (Calder & Storr 2023: 78). Where neoclassical economics’ individualist models and their statist rivals both predicted that the common pool resources would inevitably become depleted over time, unless privatised or nationalised, Ostrom showed that, in many cases, communities find ways to collectively manage resources sustainably, and founded a tradition of ‘commons scholarship’, which has ‘sought to understand the conditions under which commonly held resource use was sustainable, based on an empirical gestalt of case studies, economic games, and large-n statistical analyses’ (Quintana and Campbell 2019: 1112). As the Social Ecological Systems Framework (SESF) developed by Ostrom (2007) and refined by McGinnis and Ostrom (2014) provides the overarching theoretical framework for PRO-CLIMATE, it makes sense to choose a compatible approach to conceptualise institutions in our ABM.

There is already a substantial body of work of computational AB modelling informed by CPR theory, as identified by Oesterling et al. (2024: 429) in their multi-method analysis of the field of ABM of institutions. They highlight the analytical precision offered by Ostrom’s categorization of institutions as she developed it with co-workers over several decades, and as it has been further elaborated by others in what might be described as the CPR ‘research program’ (Lakatos 1970):

Conceptual accuracy and precision can be offered by institutional analysis approaches like the Institutional Analysis and Development [IAD] Framework and its rule-based classification of institutions (Ostrom 2005) and the Institutional Grammar and its systematic dissection of institutional statements (e.g., rules, norms) into syntactic components and discrete semantic meaning (Crawford and Ostrom 1995; Frantz and Siddiki 2022).

These analytic and classificatory tools have been used to inform the development of ABMs of both endogenous (Ghorbani & Bravo 2016) and exogenous (Zia & Koliba 2015) institutions and of their interaction (Vallino 2014). We propose to use the IAD framework and Institutional Grammar and their extensions (e.g. ‘nested ADICO’, nADICO, Franz et al. 2013) to analyse and categorise institutions for the PRO-CLIMATE MACM. nADICO adopts the ADICO scheme developed by Ostrom to classify institutions, but ‘enables a more comprehensive expression of institutions and extends the use of the original grammar into various application domains, while taking the initial step towards a more dynamic perspective on institutional modelling’ (ibid. 429).

3.3 ADICO Grammar of Institutions

The ADICO grammar consists of five components (following Franz et al. 2013, Ghorbani 2022):

– *Attributes* describe the attributes and characteristics of social entities (which can be individuals or groups) that are subject to the institutional statement (e.g. shared strategy,

norm, rule). If not specified explicitly, all attributes are assumed to be common to all individuals (or members of a group/society).

- *Deontics* – a deontic describes either an *obligation* (e.g. represented as must), *permission* (may), or a *prohibition* (must not).

- *Aim* – describes an action or outcome associated with the institutional statement. The only constraint put on an aim instance is that the action or outcome it describes must be physically possible, so that the compliance/non-compliance of an agent can be determined.

- *Conditions* – capture the circumstances under which the statement applies. This can include spatial, temporal and procedural elements. If not further constrained, the *conditions* component defaults to “at all times and in all places”.

- *Or else* – describes consequences that are associated with the violation of the institutional statement, i.e. the combination of all other components used in that statement. In Crawford and Ostrom’s grammar, this component has a constitutive role in classifying statements as rules.

The presence of different combinations of ADICO elements enables the specification of different kind of institutions; thus AIC (**A**ctor, **A**ction, **C**ondition) elements enable the specification of a convention or shared strategy, add a deontic (D) and a norm is specified, add a an ‘or else’ statement, and a rule is specified. For example:

Institution type	Elements present	Example
Convention or shared strategy	AIC (Actor, Action, Condition)	Drivers (A) produce their driving licences (I) if requested by a traffic officer (C)
Norm	ADIC (Actor, Deontic, Action, Condition)	Drivers (A) must (D) produce their driving licences (I) if requested by a traffic officer (C)
Rule	ADICO (Actor, Deontic, Action, Condition, Or else)	Drivers (A) must (D) produce their driving licences (I) if requested by a traffic officer (C) or else the traffic officer will issue a fine (O).’

3.4 Nested ADICO - nADICO

The ADICO grammar provides a semi-formal description of institutional rules that has been used to model endogenous and exogenous changes of ADICO rule statements in several SES systems (Vallino 2014; Zia and Kalibo 2015; Ghorbani & Bravo 2016: see also Smagl et al. 2010). However, it has also been criticised for inadequately capturing (i) informal social processes and (ii) the dynamic nature of much institutional formation and change (Choe and Yun 2017; Frantz et al 2013). Taking first, in ADICO ‘rules are assumed to have sanctions, whereas norms do not’ (ibid. 431); but many norms are maintained by informal social processes in the absence of formal (or explicitly specifiable) sanctions – consider shaming practices on social media, for example - and such informal processes may be highly relevant to agents in our cases, if we are to capture how a campaign organised on Facebook might impact public opinion or local politicians. Likewise, capturing the emergence and decline of institutions calls for a more flexible approach:

modelling the progression across differing institutional types requires more flexibility in specifying norms, beyond the discrete may’s, must’s, and must not’s. More flexible boundaries are desirable to support continuous adaptation so that a new and different norm may gradually emerge from or replace an existing one (ibid. 432)

To address these criticisms and increase flexibility and hence representational power and modelling realism, Frantz et al. (2013) introduced the concept of *nesting* in institutional statements.

Vertical nesting can be used to add further consequences in an ordered sequence, so C2 follows if C isn't satisfied, and so on. For example:

Drivers (A) must (D) produce their driving licences (I) if requested by a traffic officer (C)
<i>Or else Level 2:</i> the traffic officer (A2) must (D2) enforce this (I2) in any circumstances (C2)
<i>Or else Level 3:</i> internal investigators (A3) must (D3) follow up on this issue (I3) in any case (C3).

This enables the modelling of interrelations and dependencies among connected institutions – in this case traffic officers and internal investigator - but it could be municipal and regional tiers in local government in our cases monitoring say, compliance with national guidelines on protection of habitat for red listed species, for example. Thus, in the case of institutions that have a monitoring and/or enforcement role, additional institutions may be invoked and activated as a social consequence of failure to comply with some higher-level monitored statement.

Horizontal nesting enables representation of cases where norm or rule violation can have multiple consequences, for example:

Drivers (A) must (D) produce their driving licenses (I) if requested by a traffic officer (C)
<i>Or else Level 2:</i> the traffic officer (A2) must (D2) enforce this (I2) under any circumstances (C2) and, depending on severity, either issue a penalty notice (C2b) or arrest the driver (C2b)
<i>Or else Level 3:</i> internal investigators (A3) must (D3) follow up on this issue (I3) in any case (C3).

Nesting can also be used in sections of institutional statements (IS) other than *Or Else* statements to express multiple contingencies, for example to specify if (a) one of two conditions is required for an action to follow (ADIC *or* ADIC)(ADIC), or (b) if both conditions are (ADIC *and* ADIC)(ADIC). So, for example (a):

Developers (A) must (D) halt work on a site (I) if either red listed species are found to be living on the site (C1) or the development results in pollution of a water source (C2).

...and of (b):

Planners (A) must (D) decline permission to development proposal (I) if both developers have failed to complete a biodiversity assessment (C1) and there is a residents' petition with more than 1000 signatures (C2)

In many cases, we will be modelling not rules but tendencies, for example:

Planners (A) may (D) decline permission to a development proposal (I) if both developers have failed to complete a biodiversity assessment (C1) and there is a residents' petition with more than 1000 signatures (C2)

With many deontic (D) and both...and conditions (C1... n), probabilities can be assigned to the likelihood of actions (I) depending on the number of conditions (C1... n) that are met, empirical evidence etc. In this way nesting makes it possible to capture more of the likely dynamic of decision-making processes than with the simple ADICO system.

Many of the processes we will be modelling involve institutional structuring not only of constraining (monitoring and enforcement) institutions but also of enabling or opportunity providing institutions. These can also be represented in ADICO statements, which can be made more realistic using nesting. For example:

Fishers (A) may report lost equipment (D) if both NGOs promote awareness of the reporting app (C1) and the app is easy to use (C2)

Citizens (A) may sign a petition in support of protecting a natural area (D) if both NGOs promote awareness of biodiversity the area (C1) and the area has recreational value (C2)

Note that nesting may be selectively used to develop institutional statements where researchers judge that such development will add significant value in precision or realism in representation of institutional processes. In other words, it is an extension of the ADICO framework that is fully compatible with it, and which may be used at the researchers' discretion.

Ghorbani (2022) provides a detailed guide to methods for gathering data for institutional modelling using the ADICO model for different data types, including from interviews, field observations and legal documents, while Ghorbani et al.'s MAIA framework (2013) represents a comprehensive attempt to translate Ostrom's Institutional Analysis and Development Framework into an agent-based model. We will draw on both these resources in our data gathering and modelling efforts.

3.5 Social-Ecological Tipping Points and Upward Scaling Tipping Cascades

As explained in the Introduction (1.4) PRO-CLIMATE aims to identify social-ecological tipping points which may be leveraged to scale up climate change resilient actions. In complex systems, tipping events may occur sequentially in a process called a 'tipping cascade', which may be 'upwardly scaling' (self-reinforcing) if a tipping point in one subsystem triggers a larger-scale event in a second, and so on. As Sharpe and Lenton explain:

In interconnected complex systems, the activation of one tipping point can increase the likelihood of triggering another at a larger scale, and then another at a still larger scale. We call this an 'upward-scaling tipping cascade'. The progression can take place in scales that are temporal (towards a greater degree of permanence), spatial (expanding to affect a larger geographical area), or defined in terms of system boundaries (e.g. from a product, to an economic sector, to an economy of many sectors). Here we do not require that passing one tipping point makes a larger scale one inevitable, just more likely, but in the strongest case, such 'domino dynamics' can occur. (2020: 422)

They illustrate the process using the case of UK electric vehicle uptake (ibid. 426):

Figure 2. Electric vehicle tipping cascade.

We will seek to model this tipping cascade effect by investigating the interaction between tipping points in two connected systems: the social system of community mobilisation, in which we model the conditions needed for climate-change adaptive NGOs to form, and the governance system, in which we model the conditions needed for NGO mobilisation to produce climate change resilient planning decisions.

4 Integrating MOA, HUMAT and nADICO

In the previous sections we introduce the HUMAT model, as our based model for behavioural decisions, and the MOA and ADICO framework identifying the elements constraining or enabling behavioural choices and behaviour change. In this section, we will describe how we plan to integrate HUMAT with the MOA and ADICO framework (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Integrating MOA, HUMAT and nADICO

4.1 MOA → HUMAT linkage

4.1.1 Motives

The MOA framework underscores the essential role of motivations (or motives) in driving behaviour change: without motivation, behaviour change is unattainable. Similarly, in HUMAT, motives—alongside their relative importances and satisfactions—serve as the engine behind the selection of different choices. This creates a foundational link between HUMAT and MOA, predicated on the assumption that the concept of motives in HUMAT aligns with motivations in MOA.

Furthermore, HUMAT's typology of motives can be mapped onto the conceptualization of motivations in real individuals, defined as "all those brain processes that energise and direct behaviour... including habitual processes, emotional responding, as well as analytical decision-making" (Michie, van Stralen, and West 2011). In HUMAT, experiential motives would correspond to habitual and emotional motives in the real world, while values align with analytical decision-making motives. Notably, HUMAT enhances the decision-making process by considering varying degrees of importance to motives, thereby affecting their influence on choice.

Furthermore, the HUMAT framework integrates insights from other factors that influence the MOA framework. Rothschild (1999) posits that all behaviours, including altruistic ones, are fundamentally self-interested, while Schwartz's (1977) norm activation model suggests that altruistic behaviours are driven primarily by moral considerations. HUMAT incorporates both of these perspectives: agents are motivated by the satisfactions derived from their choices and opt for the choice that provides the greatest satisfaction. Consequently, altruistic behaviours in HUMAT are framed as self-satisfying and inherently self-interested. In alignment with the norm activation model, on the other hand, HUMAT equates moral considerations with value-based motives. Therefore, the identification of relevant motives, the satisfaction derived from potential choices, and the importance assigned to each motive are crucial for realistic decision-making in HUMAT.

4.1.2 Abilities

Abilities will be integrated into the HUMAT framework via two attributes: knowledge and skills. Knowledge and skills in turn will be relevant to the context of the behavioural choice agents are faced with. Knowledge and skills will affect motives in three different ways: (a) creating new motives, (b) increasing/decreasing the importance of existing motives, and (c) changing the degree of satisfaction of intention (derived from motivation) associated with a specific choice.

For instance, in the Bergen case, many Norwegian citizens have been made aware of the rate of uncoordinated natural resource loss in Norway by the NRK documentary and web article from February 2024 (the focal action point for the Bergen case). Seeing previously disconnected developments as part of an (alarming) national pattern has created *new motives for citizens to get involved in public action*, an example of (a). Second, suppose a specific development proposal involves construction work on an existing bogland site (as is the case with one of the Bergen case study sites). If citizens become aware that bogland is an important carbon sink resource (knowledge), then, if they are already motivated by concerns around climate change, this new knowledge will *heighten the salience/importance of this pre-existing motivation*, an example of (b). Third, if, in addition, galvanised by the NRK documentary and local construction proposals, citizens have, as a result, formed or joined a new Friends of the Earth chapter (as has happened at several sites in the Bergen case), then by participating in this group their campaigning skills may have been strengthened and they are likely to feel more empowered by working with others for a common cause, both *increasing the satisfaction of their motivation to positively impact their environment*, an example of (c).

Further, when in a non-social dilemma, HUMAT agents may try to increase their abilities (knowledge and skills) by inquiring about others in their social network. This increase will then have the three potential consequences for motives mentioned above.

4.1.3 Opportunities

Opportunities are considered enablers of behaviours. They can facilitate behaviour change either by increasing motivation to make a specific behavioural choice or by creating entirely new behavioural options. In real life, this can be achieved through various approaches, such as offering incentives that encourage a particular behaviour, building new physical infrastructures that make it easier to choose a certain behaviour, or even generating alternative behavioural choices. In the model, incentives and environmental changes can modify the importance of agents' motives and/or the satisfaction derived from their choices, ultimately leading to behaviour change.

4.2 ADICO → MOA linkage

Institutional statements will directly affect the three elements of the MOA framework (motivations, opportunities and abilities), as well as the behavioural choices available to the individuals. Institutions generate statements that can vary in the presence/absence of the *Deontic* and *Or else* attributes. Thus, the type of statement generated will depend on the type of institution. For instance, governmental institutions can generate all kinds of statements whereas others such as NGOs may only be able to generate statements without the *Or else* attribute. Hence, in the model, just as in the ADICO framework, institutions will generate statements of the following type: shared strategy, norm, or rule.

Further, following the intervention framework suggested by Rotschild (1999), types of statements can be mapped to the type of interventions: education, marketing, and law. For instance, educational statements can be of the type shared strategy or norm, since they can have the Deontic attribute but not the *Or else* one. Marketing and law statements on the other hand, can be of the three types: shared strategy, norm, or rule. Yet, whereas in marketing statements the *Or else* attribute may be of a positive nature (e.g., a reward), in the law statement this attribute will tend to be of a negative nature (e.g., fine or punishment).

Mapping statement types onto interventions will allow us to identify how the statements may modify the MOA elements. Educational statements will modify the following MOA elements and sub-elements. Education can affect abilities (via knowledge and skills) and choices' satisfactions. For instance, educational statements may increase the knowledge of individuals and ultimately may affect the importance of its motivation(s). Likewise, education, like training, may affect the skills of the individuals and, in turn, modify choices and satisfactions. Finally, education, like persuasion messages, can have a direct effect on the satisfaction linked to choices by increasing or decreasing the feeling of satisfaction derived from a choice. Marketing statements can affect the satisfactions of choices or create new choices. For instance, incentives or subsidies create the expectation of a reward thereby affecting the satisfaction associated with choices. Similarly, changes in the physical environment may create new choices. For instance, creating a new bike path may allow individuals to bike, instead of going by car or taking public transportation. Finally, legal statements can also affect the satisfaction of choices, via the expectation of a punishment or a cost. Similarly, law statements can hinder certain choices. For instance, the restriction of the sale of alcohol to individuals over 18 years old can reduce the sale of alcohol and intoxication rate of underage individuals.

Community level factors such as peer pressure or social norms are other factors thought to influence behavioural change. In HUMAT, individuals are embedded in social networks that influence the selected behavioural choice. First, in HUMAT agents have a social motive that determines the satisfaction they obtain from a behavioural choice, which is directly proportional to the percentage of individuals selecting the given behaviours in the individuals' social network. Hence, individuals are directly influenced by the behaviours of others. Further, whenever in a social dilemma, individuals set out to influence the behavioural decision of others by actively informing others about their choices and making them reevaluate them. Furthermore, individuals have a level of persuasion, so that those with a higher level will be more persuasive than others. Thus, HUMAT, considers, not only the individual level, but, also, the community level factors posited by Andreasen (2002), i.e., social norms, interpersonal influence, diffusion processes and local leadership.

5 Model conceptualization applied to the Bergen case study

In this section we identify the abilities, opportunities and motivations for the Bergen case. Via examples, we illustrate interrelationships among them, and how actors in the model affect each of these elements. For instance, government, NGOs, and other institutions may generate different statements and thus influence different MOA elements, as described previously. Here we give examples of this. Through surveys, interviews, document analysis and observation we will identify the motives, motives' importances, and behavioural choices, and choices satisfactions of actors and institutions in the Bergen case.

Description of the problem

The problem is loss of natural resources (and hence the climate change adaptive capacity they contain) across Norway (especially in Vestland, the region of which Bergen is the capital) through un-coordinated land development (for infrastructure, residential and industrial purposes).

Individuals (persons) involved. These include politicians (who have power in decision making processes), planners (who provide information and advice to politicians, informing those decisions, mapping land use and informing on legal and policy parameters); farmers and property developers with a stake in economic exploitation of land; and I suggest perhaps two categories of citizens - rural poor/unemployed who might have a particularly strong stake in local economic development over environmental concerns, and environmental activists (strongly motivated towards nature conservation).

Institutions involved

- Government institutions e.g. municipality/district (*kommune*) planning departments that advise the councils on relevant policy and regulatory framework (precise remit in relation to planning process can be established through interviews); councils (elected bodies that vote on planning decisions); regional government (*fylke*) represent central government at the regional level; can over-rule *kommune* decisions in certain cases, promote good practice e.g. through use of planning tools to better map land use.
- NGOs (e.g. Friends of the Earth Norway (*Naturvernforbundet*) - new local branches established in response to NRK documentary on rapid loss of natural habitats due to uncoordinated development. Mobilize through social media, local leafleting & meetings (e.g. Pro-Coast *Askøy Kildn/Eidsvika* case).
- Private sector - development companies, builders & other contractors (e.g. *Tertnes Holdings* for *Askøy* case).

Together with natural and built environment and other species within it, human agents and institutions constitute a social-ecological system (SES), defined by the IPBES as 'complex adaptive systems in which people and nature are inextricably linked, in which both the social and ecological components exert strong influence over outcomes. The social dimension includes actors, institutions, cultures and economies, including livelihoods. The ecological dimension includes wild species and the ecosystem they inhabit.' (IPBES 2024)

In our case this therefore includes the individual actors and institutions mentioned above, plus also the physical environment and its biodiversity. The region largely consists of coastal islands and peninsulas linked by bridges, tunnels and ferry crossings, with various habitats including wetlands, marshes, forests and grazing land. There are some red listed species at the case study sites. Decisions on construction projects impact the viability of habitats for species as well as the carbon and water absorption capacity of the land, already impacted by heavy and (due to climate change) increasingly heavy and seasonally focused (more in Autumn winter, less in spring/summer) rainfall, increasing flood risk.

Type of behavioural change aimed for

As stated in the research questions, we are interested both in (a) the conditions under which citizens form groups and initiate campaigning, and (b) in the conditions under which these actions impact on decision making which in turn impacts on the local environment. So, the specific behaviours are (a) environmental group formation and (b) environmental decision making, with different sets of actors involved in each - primarily individuals for (a) and primarily institutions for (b).

Table 1 presents examples of institutional statements for the Bergen case created using the nADICO institutional grammar (Frantz et al. 2013).

Table 1: Examples of nADICO institutional statements from the Bergen case

Institution	nADICO statement type	Intervention statement type	Example of nADICO statements describing the action of each institution	MOA/HUMAT element affected
Fylke (regional government)	Rules and laws ADIC	Law	Regional government (A) will veto (D) planning proposals passed by local councils if either (a) a proposed site has red-listed species living/nesting there (C1) or (b) the proposal contravenes some aspect of national environmental policy (C2)	Opportunity & Action (OA)
Local government (kommune)	Rule and laws ADIC	Law	Local councils (A) will decline permission (D) to a development proposal (I) if either developers have failed complete a biodiversity assessment (C1) or there is a residents' petition with more than 1000 signatures (C2)	Opportunity & Action (OA)
FoE (activist NGO)	Norms AIC	Education	Local environmental NGOs (A) will organise campaigns against developments (I) if either they perceive the local environment is threatened (C1) or that development will negatively impact climate goals (C2)	Motivation (M)
Developer	Conventions and norms AIC	Marketing	Local investment consortia (A) will promote local developments (I) if they both perceive that it will be profitable for investors (C1) and that it aligns with local values (C2)	Motivation (M)

6 Next Steps

The next step of the process is detailed design of the model, elaborating the properties of agents and institutions using data collected from the Bergen case and developed using data from the other case studies and relevant literature. We believe the model can work for a range of cases where there is a common pool resource/threat (land, water, air, carbon sink) and where two levels of social interaction are relevant (as outlined at 1.2 and elaborated at 1.4). We will work closely with partners to support them to gather data in ways that will help us to develop the model.

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